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SHAKESPEARE 'S CREATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENGLISH LITERATURE

Berdimurodova Surayyo Baxodir qizi

*Student of the Termiz State Pedagogical Institute, majoring in foreign language
and literature (Euro-English).*

Adilova Muhabbat Asadovna

*Russian language teacher, Department of Uzbek language and literature
(languages), Termiz Institute of Agrotechnologies and Innovative Development*

Shakespeare's literary heritage consists of poetry and drama. The epics "Venus and Adonis" (1593) and "Lucretsia" (1594) related to Roman history, which he wrote on the basis of a mythological plot, were warmly welcomed. These works, especially the "Sonnets" written in the years 1592-1600, showed that Shakespeare appeared in an integral relationship with the culture of the Renaissance. Shakespeare's sonnets, which are among the great examples of world lyrics, are divided into 2 groups in terms of subject matter: the first 126 sonnets are dedicated to the poet's close friend, while sonnets 127-152 describe the lyrical hero's feelings of love and suffering towards his unfaithful lover. Although Shakespeare wrote several other epics, the issue of their authorship is still disputed.

The publication dates of Shakespeare's works correspond to the time when they were neither written nor performed. There were times when Shakespeare wrote parts 2-3 first, and then part 1 of his works consisting of several parts.

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Therefore, literary experts prefer to study Shakespeare's dramaturgical works in 4 periods: 1st period - 1590-94, 2nd period 1594-1600, third period 1600-1608, fourth period 1609-1613. In the 1st period of Shakespeare's dramatic work, in addition to the epic, the first tragedy ("Titus Andronicus") and comedies ("Comedy of Errors", "The Temptation of the Maiden"), "Henry VI" (part 2, 1590), "Henry VI" (3rd part, 1591), "Henry VI" (1st part, 1592), "Richard III" (1593) wrote the first chronicles. In the 2nd period, "Richard II" (1595), a "near-tragedy chronicle", "Henry IV" (Part 1, 1597), "Henry IV" (Part 2, 1598) and (1594), "A Midsummer Night's Dream", " He wrote the romantic comedies "Merchant of Venice" (1596) and the tragedy "Romeo and Juliet" (1595). His famous comedies such as "A tumult out of nowhere" (1598), "Twelfth Night" (1600) were also published during this period.

The masterpieces of the playwright are "Julius Caesar" (1599), "Hamlet" (1601), "Othello" (1604), "King Lear" (1605), "Macbeth" (1606), "Antony and Cleopatra", "Coriolanus". "(1607) tragedies form the 3rd period of Shakespeare's work. The chronicle "Henry VIII" (1613), "The Winter's Tale" (1611), "The Tempest" (1612) and romantic dramas and tragedies are the products of Shakespeare's late works.

Shakespeare effectively used Holinshed's "Chronicle of England, Scotland and Ireland", rich in plots related to the history of England, in creating his works. Plutarch's "Comparative Biographies" on the scene of Shakespeare's historical tragedies and M. Bandello's comedies

Italian Renaissance stories served as the main source. Based on the plots of such tragedies as "Romeo and Juliet", "Hamlet", "King Lear", stage works were

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created even before Shakespeare. But these plots served as a vital source in the creation of immortal works expressing universal thoughts and ideas due to Shakespeare's great dramaturgical skill. Along with studying the history, literature and theater of the European nations before him, Shakespeare also enjoyed the fruits of advanced thinking of the 17th century, and based on this, he embodied them with great artistic power in his best works. As observed in every historical period, the period in which Shakespeare lived was not without contradictions and contradictions. Shakespeare, unlike other writers, sensitively felt such conflicts in the life of his time, the complexities of social life and the fate of people, and was not satisfied with this, he paid special attention to portraying the drama that occurred at the critical point of society and human life. As a real dramatist, he revealed the social, domestic, spiritual and spiritual reasons that caused this or that behavior of the characters, and made it possible for each of them to fully justify or explain the sudden changes in their behavior.

In the 2nd period of Shakespeare's work, he appeared as a master of poetic drama. During this period, he did not give up the methods of confrontation paying great attention to drama, combined tragic and comic motives.

As a result, dramatic lyricism reached its climax in Shakespeare's works ("Romeo and Juliet", "Richard II", "Twelfth Night"). In the 3rd period of Shakespeare's work, works belonging to the genre of tragedy take the leading place. Playwright

Seeing the conflict between the ideas of humanism and humanitarianism characteristic of the Renaissance period and the increasingly developing selfishness, hypocrisy, and evil in reality, he draws these conflicts into his works as

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a conflict. He reached the peak of artistic skill in the tragedies he created in the same period. Romantic dramas and tragic comedies of the last period of Shakespeare's work testify to the hope that life conflicts can be solved positively in his worldview.

The quality that illuminates all of Shakespeare's work is the image of high moral and spiritual problems. While "Romeo and Juliet" is considered lyrical, "Julius Caesar" is political, "Hamlet" is an intellectual tragedy, and "Ogello" is a tragedy of passions, at the heart of them lie moral issues that are of great importance both for medieval works and for the present time. If the dramatic conflict described in works such as "Julius Caesar", "Hamlet", "Macbeth", "Romeo and Juliet" allowed the characters to know themselves and realize their spiritual strength, then the mind of lost characters such as Othello and Lear is inevitable only when a tragedy occurs. only when doom approaches does it become radiant. Nevertheless, each of them and the heroes of Shakespeare's works in general are mostly strong and courageous people with a strong character, a well-formed mind and moral views, a watchful eye on reality.

Shakespeare also created great works of art in the genres of comedy and tragicomedy. The theme of love that overcomes all obstacles is at the center of his comedies full of adventure, imbued with the romance of the Renaissance, depicting scenes of rural life. As in Shakespeare's tragedies, the speech of the characters in his comedies is full of sharp and deep thoughts, jokes and jokes.

The discovery of Shakespeare by the Uzbek audience began in 1935 with the staging of the tragedy "Hamlet" at the Hamza Drama Theater (now the Uzbek National Academic Drama Theater). After that, in Uzbek and Russian theaters in

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Uzbekistan, Shakespeare's Othello, Romeo and Juliet, Julius Caesar, King Lear, Coriolanus, Two Boys from Verona, The Casting of the Maiden, Strange Horses on a Summer Night such works were staged with great success. Writers and translators such as Gafur Ghulam, Yashin, Uygun, Shaikhzada, Turob Tola, Q. Mirmuhamedov took part in the translation of Shakespeare's works. In recent years, Jamal Kamal directly translated Shakespeare's works from English into Uzbek.

